

High Strain Rate Characterization of Angle-Ply Glass/Epoxy Laminates

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ABSTRACT

A direct tension split Hopkinson bar apparatus and servo-hydraulic testing machines were used to investigate the effect of strain rate on the mechanical behavior of Scotchply Type 1002 glass/epoxy angle-ply laminates. Tests were conducted at strain rates of approximately 10^{-5} 1/sec and 10^3 1/sec. Results indicate that the maximum normal stress experienced by glass/epoxy laminates is higher for dynamic loading conditions than for static. Both the fibers and matrix are sensitive to the strain rate. The rate sensitivity of the fibers, however, appears to influence the laminate rate sensitivity more than the matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

The split Hopkinson bar technique, introduced by Kolsky [1], is the most widely used method for studying material behavior at deformation rates between 100 1/sec and 10,000 1/sec. In this technique, a short material specimen is placed between two bars. The specimen is loaded by a stress wave generated in one of the bars (loading bar). Once the specimen is loaded, a portion of the loading wave propagates through to the second (output) bar, while part reflects back to the loading bar. The history of load and deformation in the specimen are established by monitoring the stress waves as they propagate through the bars, which remain elastic during the test. The technique was initially used for specimens loaded in compression, but has been modified for tension and torsion loading. A variety of methods have been developed for generating tension waves using this technique. A cup shaped specimen was introduced by Lindholm and Yeakley [2]. Tension in the cup's rim is produced by supporting the cup rim and pushing the bottom out with a standard compression wave. Nicholas [3] introduced a procedure by which tension is generated by reflection of a compression wave which initially bypasses the specimen. Harding and Welsh [4] generated tension waves in composites by direct impact of a yoke connected to the end of the input bar. Staab and Gilat [5] produce direct tension by releasing a stored load applied to one end of the input bar. A review of many of the available tensile Hopkinson apparatus is given by Nicholas and Bless [6] and by Nicholas [7].

2. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

The high strain rate tests conducted in this study employ the direct tension split Hopkinson bar apparatus developed by Staab and Gilat [5]. A schematic representation of the

apparatus and elastic wave fronts is shown in Figure 1. A tensile wave is generated in the input bar by release of a load initially stored at the end section.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of direct tension split Hopkinson bar apparatus

The stress wave in the bars is monitored by strain gages located as shown in Figure 1. Two 1000 Ω axial gages are placed at each location along the bar, and two 1000 Ω dummy gages are used for each location to complete a full Wheatstone bridge. Flexural waves which may be transmitted through the specimen are monitored by a full Wheatstone bridge consisting of 350 Ω gages, applied to the output bar. Signals from the bridges are recorded on a Nicolet 4094 oscilloscope which is also used for data processing.

Two sets of specimens, one for dynamic tests, and the other for quasi-static tests were prepared. For both type of tests, the specimen is a rectangular $[\pm\theta]_s$ laminate made from Scotchply Type 1002 glass/epoxy. Laminated sheets with fiber orientations of $[\pm 15]_s$, $[\pm 30]_s$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ were prepared in a lamination press following the manufacturer's suggested curing procedure. The $[\pm 15]_s$ and $[\pm 30]_s$ sheets were used for the preparation of $[\pm 60]_s$ and $[\pm 75]_s$ specimens. Specimens for dynamic testing were prepared by initially cutting dog-bone shape coupons from the cured sheets. The dog-bone design is required since glue is used to affix the specimens to appropriate holders and the bars, and a large area for shear transfer is needed to transmit load from the input bar into the specimen. The dog-bone specimen is glued to two slotted cylinders, which are subsequently glued between the input and output bars with an adhesive. The dog-bone coupon and slotted cylinder assemblies are shown schematically in Figure 2. Specimens for static tests were straight coupons extracted from the same sheets as the dog-bone specimens. With the exception of the $[\pm 15]_s$ specimens, they were glued (with the same adhesive) into slotted cylindrical holders similar to those used for dynamic testing. Uniaxial strain gages applied to both sides of each specimen were used to monitor strain and possible bending. Each holder was pinned to a dual direction universal joint fitting, which was secured to the testing machine. This further reduced the possibility of introducing an eccentric moment into the specimen. Measured strains from gages on both sides were essentially identical, and were averaged to define the strain for each specimen. Static tests involving the dual direction universal joint fitting were conducted using a conventional servo-hydraulic Instron testing machine. Tests for the $[\pm 15]_s$ specimens were conducted in a different manner. At shallower fiber angles the force required to produce specimen failure at quasi-static strain rates is generally greater than the shear strength of the

adhesive. Therefore, end tabs were applied to the $[\pm 15]_s$ specimens and they were tested using wedge action grips on a servo-hydraulic MTS testing machine.

Figure 2. Dog-bone composite specimen and cylindrical holder geometry

Assuming the deformation of the specimen is homogeneous, the strain rate in a split Hopkinson bar can be expressed as

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\dot{x}_i - \dot{x}_o}{\ell} \quad (1)$$

where \dot{x}_i and \dot{x}_o are the linear velocities of the specimens on the input and output sides of the bar, respectively, and ℓ is the specimen length. The velocities of each side of the specimen at time t are determined from elastic wave theory, and are expressed as

$$\dot{x}_i = \frac{1}{\rho A c} \left[F_A \left(t - \frac{L_A}{c} \right) + F_A \left(t - \frac{L_A}{c} + 2 \frac{L_B}{c} \right) - F_B \left(t - \frac{L_B}{c} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{x}_o = \frac{1}{\rho A c} \left[F_C \left(t - \frac{L_C}{c} \right) \right]$$

where ρ , A and c are the density, cross-sectional area and the uniaxial wave speed of the bar, respectively. The distances L_A , L_B and L_C are referenced from each corresponding gage location to the specimen, and F_A , F_B and F_C are the forces measured at each gage location. The strain rate in the specimen (equation (1)) can be controlled by the length and area of the specimen and the amplitude of the stored load. The normal stress in the specimen can be expressed as

$$\sigma(t) = \frac{F_A}{A_s} \left(t - \frac{L_C}{c} \right) \quad (3)$$

where A_s is the cross-sectional area of the specimen.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 16 dynamic and 15 static tests were conducted. The strain rate for the dynamic tests ranged from 958 to 1519 1/sec. All quasi-static tests were conducted at approximately the same rate of 6.75×10^{-5} 1/sec. As an example of raw data obtained in the split Hopkinson bar, the tensile waves recorded at each of the three strain gage locations for a typical experiment (EXP 92-14, a $[\pm 45]_s$ specimen) are shown in Figure 3. A rise time of approximately 40 μsec is observed in the loading wave, and is typical of all tests. Following the rise time the input wave is relatively smooth. The strain rate in the specimen is obtained by manipulating the recorded waves according to equations 1 and 2. The strain rate for a typical experiment (EXP 92-14) is shown in Figure 4. All plots presented in this paper are obtained from the recorded raw data. Data has not been smoothed or averaged electronically or numerically.

Figure 3. Wave profiles recorded at strain gage locations A, B and C for EXP 92-14

Figure 4. Typical strain rate profile (EXP 92-14)

Stress-strain diagrams of $[\pm 15]_S$, $[\pm 30]_S$, $[\pm 45]_S$, $[\pm 60]_S$ and $[\pm 75]_S$ test specimens are shown in Figures 5, through 9, respectively. In the quasi-static tests for the $[\pm 30]_S$ laminates, only one specimen (EXP 92-4) failed in the gage section. The other two specimens failed prematurely in the grip region. Similarly, in the quasi-static tests of $[\pm 15]_S$ laminates, only one specimen (EXP 93-9) failed in the gage region, while the others failed in the grip region. The strain record for the $[\pm 15]_S$ specimen which failed in the gage region is not complete, since the lead wires on both gages disconnected from the gages during testing. The maximum load, however, was recorded for this specimen.

Figure 5. Dynamic stress-strain curves for $[\pm 15]_S$ laminates

Figure 6. Static and dynamic stress-strain curves for $[\pm 30]_S$ laminates

Complete (static and dynamic) results have been obtained for the $[\pm 45]_S$, $[\pm 60]_S$ and $[\pm 75]_S$ laminates. All of the results show a strain rate effect in which the stresses to failure are higher in the dynamic tests.

Figure 7. Static and dynamic stress-strain curves for $[\pm 45]_S$ laminates

Figure 8. Static and dynamic stress-strain curves for $[\pm 60]_s$ laminates

Figure 9. Static and dynamic stress-strain curves for $[\pm 75]_s$ laminates

The average maximum normal stress from dynamic and static tests for each angle-ply configuration is presented in Figure 10 as a function of ply orientation. In addition to the results from this investigation, the manufacturer's specified failure strengths for cross-ply laminates at two different testing angles are also shown. The manufacturer's failure stresses agree well with

the results from quasi-static tests presented herein. From Figure 10 it is obvious that rate effects are more dominant at shallower fiber orientation angles. This implies that the rate sensitivity of fibers contributes more to the overall rate effect of the laminate than does the rate sensitivity of the matrix.

Figure 10. Maximum normal stress variation with angle-ply fiber orientation

4. CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary results presented herein indicate that the mechanical response characteristics of angle-ply laminates made from Scotchply Type 1002 glass/epoxy are rate sensitive. Direct tensile loads at strain rates in the neighborhood of 1000 1/sec have a marked influence on the maximum normal stress in a specimen. Results from tests at shallower fiber orientations show a more significant variation between static and dynamic responses than do large angles. This implies that although the rate sensitivity effects of each constituent contributes to the overall laminate response, the rate sensitivity of the fibers appears to be the most influential.

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